

Hermeneutics Through Dictionary

Subtheme : Towards Global Best Teaching Learning Process In Indian Higher Education

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Purpose – Hermeneutics as the document (Department of English, 2020) describes is an art of understanding and to make oneself understood. The purpose of the research paper is to find whether different dictionaries published by different publishers are spreading the same knowledge or vary in content .The purpose is also to understand what are the various sources which contribute in etymology .

Design/Methodology/Approach – The research design is exploratory and research type is Exploratory and Descriptive.The research papers were selected randomly for review and 3 different dictionaries ((2011), (Hawker, 2014)(Kumar, et al., 2014)) were used to find the meanings of unknown words and then compared and there were differences observed which may be due to various factors .A sample of 30 random words was selected and their meanings were found and it was explored whether there was a significant difference between the meanings stated in dictionary 1 and dictionary 2 , 3 .Z test for proportion is applied to map the difference .

Findings –Variation in meanings were observed in the 3 dictionaries .The research study also brings forward a point that different disciplines have different principles which create conflict .For eg: Quality Management aims at Customer Focus to fulfill the requirements of the customer who want clarity in understanding meanings of words which can be enhanced by using standardized content.The English language gives the freedom of construction (Gen1)to authors which may be a hindrance in developing common understanding .The dictionaries are not merged completely with other discipline words like Maths , Quality Management etc hence there is a need to study the process of word inclusion in any dictionary .

Practical implications –Dictionary is commonly used by all students irrespective of their level of education and there exists variation due to different publications , usage , different

editions etc. The big question is whether the sole purpose of the dictionary to enhance understanding among users is sustained or not .

Originality/value – The cause and effect diagram for content variation in dictionary is the first of it’s kind as the application of elementary Quality Assurance tools to dictionary content is rare .Also , it brings forward an important point that being at different levels of understanding may not always be because of different knowledge level but it may be because of the different sources (eg :Dictionary) people are using to enhance and develop their understanding .

Keywords : Cause and Effect Diagram , Hermeneutics , Quality Management, Customer focus ,Construction

Hermeneutics Through Dictionary

1.Introduction

Principles on which a discipline is based are the firm guiding beliefs and sometimes there is a situation when there are clashes between guiding principles of different disciplines .

Table 1 Comparison of conflicting principles of English and Quality Management Discipline

Principle	Customer Focus	Construction
Discipline	Quality Management	English
Meaning	The customer expectations should be fulfilled .	The author can use words relative to other words to construct the meaning he desires to .
Description in present case	As customers of dictionary users expect to know the meanings of unknown words which they read/listen in day to day activities .Knowing the meanings help them communicate smoothly without conflict . If users have dictionaries with different content they might not be able	Flexibility is given to the author to use words to derive his/her own desired meaning .This does not promote standardized content .

	<p>to understand each other well . Also , whenever there are changes in word usage to derive a new meaning the changes should be communicated to the user so that they can buy updated versions of the dictionary.They should have access to updated versions .The expectation of the users is standardized content with standard meanings .eg :If a user has the dictionary (Hawker, 2014) and he/she is discussing plight then his/her understanding of plight might differ from the user of dictionary (2011) as the meaning given is promise of faith and loyalty with deep sincerity .</p>	
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2.Literature Review

The 7 papers (Anand) (BYadav and S.Pingle) (Chaturvedi Joohi) (Chhadva and Kacker) (Chris Watkins) (Hooda and Jain) (Worku) related to keyword “ Effectiveness “ were reviewed alongwith some sections of 2 books (M.Mahajan) (Ravishankar) as additional readings .The words of which meanings were not known were found and segregated and their meanings were looked in all the 3 dictionaries (Hawker, 2014) (2011) (Kumar, et al., 2014) and listed in the table shown below .

Table 2 Sampled words and their meanings in the 3 different dictionaries .

Source	S.No.	Word	Little Oxford Dictionary	Illustrated Oxford Dictionary	Oxford English-English Hindi Dictionary
	Published by		Oxford University Press	Dorling Kindersley Limited and Oxford University Press	Oxford University Press
	Year of Publication		2006	2011	2014
			ISBN-13:978-0-19-568449-0 ISBN-10:0-19-568449-4	978-0-1434-1621-0	0-19-807640-1
(Chhadva, et al., 2013)	1	Plight (noun)	a dangerous or difficult situation	a dangerous or difficult situation	a bad or difficult state or situation
		plit (french)		fold	
		(verb)	promise to marry		NOT FOUND
		(be plighted to)-old english		(be plighted to) be engaged to be married to	
				solemnly promise faith or loyalty	
(Worku, 2019)	2	succint (adjective)	briefly and clearly expressed	briefly and clearly expressed	said clearly in a few words
		succinctly(adverb)			
		succingere (latin)		tuck up	
	3	eclectic (adjective)	taking ideas from a wide range of sources	using ideas from a wide variety of sources	NOT FOUND
		eclectically (adverb)	NOT FOUND		NOT FOUND
		eclecticism (noun)	NOT FOUND		NOT FOUND
		eklektikos (greek)	NOT FOUND		NOT FOUND
	4	tenet (noun)	a central principle or belief	a central principle or belief	one of the principles or beliefs that a theory or larger set of beliefs is based on
	latin	NOT FOUND	he holds	NOT FOUND	
(Ravishankar, 2010)	5	impregnable (adjective)	unable to be captured or broken into	unable to be captured or broken into	NOT FOUND
			unable to be defeated	unable to be overcome	
		imprenable (old french)	NOT FOUND		NOT FOUND
(Chaturvedi Jooi, 2015)	6	incessant (adjective)	never stopping	never stopping	never stopping (and usually annoying)

		incessantly (adverb)	(no meaning-only word written)	(no meaning-only word written)	(no meaning-only word written)	
		latin origin	NOT FOUND		NOT FOUND	
(Worku, 2019)	7	vogue (noun)	the fashion or style current at a particular time	the fashion or style current at a particular time	a fashion for something	
		voguish (adjective)	NOT FOUND		NOT FOUND	
		french origin	NOT FOUND		NOT FOUND	
	8	entangle (verb)	cause something to become tangled (twist together into a knotted mass)		usually be entangled in/with 1.make tangled	caught in something else
				involve someone in complicated circumstances	2.involve someone in a complicated situation	NOT FOUND
		entanglement (noun)	(no meaning-only word written)	(no meaning-only word written)	NOT FOUND	
	9	impasse (noun)	a situation in which no progress is possible	a situation in which no progress is possible; deadlock	a difficult situation in which no progress can be made because the people involved can't agree what to do	
			french origin			
(BYadav, et al., 2016)	10	intact (adjective)	not damaged	not damaged	not damaged	
		intactus (latin)		untouched	complete	
	11	stressor	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND	
	12	formative (adjective)	having a strong influence in the way something is formed	having a strong influence in the development of something	having an important and lasting influence (on somebody's character and opinions)	
	13	spurt (verb)	gush out in a stream	gush out in a sudden stream	(about a liquid) to come out quickly with great force , to make a liquid do this	
				move with a sudden burst of speed	move with a sudden burst of speed	to suddenly increase your speed or effort
		noun	a gushing stream	a sudden gushing stream	NOT FOUND	
			a sudden burst of activity or speed	a sudden burst of activity or speed	NOT FOUND	

	14	intervene (verb)	become involved in a situation in order to improve or control it	come between 2 people or things so as to alter or prevent a situation	to act in a way that prevents something happening or influences the result of something
			2.happen in the time or space between other things		to interrupt somebody who is speaking in order to say something
					to happen in a way that delays something or stops something from happening
		intervention (noun)		the action of coming between people or things to improve or control a situation	
		intervening (adjective)		occurring between or among	Coming or existing between 2 events , dates , objects etc .
		intervenire (Latin)			
	15	turmoil (noun)	a state of great disturbance , confusion , or uncertainty	a state of great disturbance , confusion , or uncertainty	a state of great noise or confusion
	16	didactic (adjective)	intended to teach or give moral instruction	intended to teach or give moral guidance	designed to teach people something especially a moral lesson
					telling people things rather than letting them find out for themselves
		didactically (adverb)	NOT FOUND		
		didacticism (noun)	NOT FOUND		NOT FOUND
		didaskein		teach	
	17	impetus (noun)	the force or energy with which something moves	the force or energy with which a body moves	NOT FOUND
			the force that makes something happen	a driving force	something that encourages something else to happen
		latin		assault,force	
	18	suboptimal	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND
	19	caveat(noun)	warning	a warning	NOT FOUND
		caveat(latin)		let a person beware	
(Anand, 2019)	20	conjunction (noun)	a word used to connect words or clauses	a word used to connect words or clauses	a word that is used for joining other words,phrases or sentences

			an instance of 2 or more things happening at the same time or being in the same place	an instance of 2 or more events occurring together	NOT FOUND
	21	ocular (adjective)	having to do with the eyes	relating to the eyes or vision	NOT FOUND
		oculus (latin)		eye	
	22	innumeros	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND
	23	cumbersome (adjective)	difficult to carry or use because of it's size or weight	difficult to use or carry through size or weight	heavy and difficult to carry , use , wear etc.
			complicated and time consuming	complicated and inefficient or time consuming	(used about a system etc .)slow and complicated
(Hooda, et al., 2018)	24	benchmark (noun)	a standard against which things may be compared	a standard against which things may be compared	a standard that other things can be compared to
	25	reliable (adjective)	able to be depended on or trusted	able to be depended on or trusted	that you can trust
		reliably (adverb)	(no meaning-only word written)	(no meaning-only word written)	(no meaning-only word written)
		reliability (noun)	(no meaning-only word written)	(no meaning-only word written)	(no meaning-only word written)
(M.Mahajan)	26	craftsman(noun)	a worker who is skilled in a particular craft	a worker skilled in a particular craft	a person who makes things skillfully,especially with his/her hands
		craftsmanship (noun)	(no meaning-only word written)	(no meaning-only word written)	the skill used by somebody to make something of high quality with his/her hands
(Chris Watkins, 2002)	27	accentuate (verb)	make a feature more noticeable	make more noticeable	to emphasize something or make something easier to notice
		accentuation (noun)		(no meaning-only word written)	NOT FOUND
	28	collegial (adjective)	NOT FOUND	also collegiate (relating to a college or its students)	NOT FOUND
				(of a university)composed of different colleges	
	29	multiethnic	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND
	30	repertoire (noun)	material known or regularly performed by a performer or company	the works known or regularly performed by a performer or company	all the plays or music that an actor or a musician knows and can perform

					all the things that a person is able to do
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3. Research Methodology

Research Design – Exploratory type as based on secondary data .

Research Type – Exploratory and Descriptive

Sampling – Non Random Type of Sampling as papers were searched with keyword effectiveness

Purposive Sampling – Paper were selected at the sole discretion of the author

Data Type – Secondary

Statistical Tests – Z test for proportion

4. Hypothesis Formulation and Testing

Table 3 Types of variation observed in the 3 dictionaries

Based on above figure following hypothesis are formulated-

Terminologies

Dictionary 1(D1) -(Hawker, 2014)

Dictionary 2(D2)- (DK Illustrated Oxford Dictionary, 2011)

Dictionary 3(D3) -(Kumar & Sahai, 2014)

Table 4 Hypothesis and description

S.No	Hypothesis	Criteria	Description
1	H ₀₁ H _{a1}	Derivatives given for each word + origin of word	It is believed that there is no significant difference observed in the proportion of (derivatives +origin) of words given in the dictionary 1 and 2 . It is believed that there is a significant difference observed in the proportion of (derivatives +origin) of words given in the dictionary 1 and 2 .
2	H ₀₂ H _{a2}		It is believed that there is no significant difference observed in the proportion of (derivatives + origin) of words given in the dictionary 2 and 3 . It is believed that there is a significant difference observed in the proportion of (derivatives + origin) of words given in the dictionary 2 and 3 .
3	H ₀₃ H _{a3}		It is believed that there is no significant difference observed in the proportion of (derivatives + origin)of words given in the dictionary 3 and 1 . It is believed that there is a significant difference observed in the proportion of (derivatives + origin) of words given in the dictionary 3 and 1 .
4	H ₀₄ H _{a4}	Similarity in Meanings of words given	It is believed that there is no significant difference observed in the proportion of words having same meanings given in the dictionary 1 and 2 to the maximum possible proportion of words having same meanings in the dictionary 1 and 2 . It is believed that there is a significant difference observed in the proportion of words having same meanings given in the dictionary 1 and 2 to the maximum possible proportion of words having same meanings in the dictionary 1 and 2 .
5	H ₀₅ H _{a5}		It is believed that there is no significant difference observed in the proportion of words having same meanings given in the dictionary 2 and 3 to the

		<p>maximum possible proportion of words having same meanings in the dictionary 2 and 3 .</p> <p>It is believed that there is a significant difference observed in the proportion of words having same meanings given in the dictionary 2 and 3 to the maximum possible proportion of words having same meanings in the dictionary 2 and 3 .</p>
6	<p>H_{06}</p> <p>H_{a6}</p>	<p>It is believed that there is no significant difference observed in the proportion of words having same meanings given in the dictionary 3 and 1 to the maximum possible proportion of words having same meanings in the dictionary 3 and 1 .</p> <p>It is believed that there is a significant difference observed in the proportion of words having same meanings given in the dictionary 3 and 1 to the maximum possible proportion of words having same meanings in the dictionary 3 and 1 .</p>

5.Results and Findings

5.1 Results

The distribution of derivatives and origin of words is distributed in the 3 dictionaries as shown below .

Figure 1 Distribution of derivatives and origin of words given in the 3 dictionaries

The methodology adopted for comparison of word meanings is shown below –

Score	Description	Example
1	If meanings are same in 2 dictionaries.	Caveat is a warning according to (Hawker) and (DK Illustrated Oxford Dictionary) hence given score 1 .
0.5	If meanings match partially in 2 dictionaries.	Impasse means a situation in which no progress is possible according to (DK Illustrated Oxford Dictionary) and a difficult situation in which no progress is made because the people involved cant agree what to do according to (Dr Suresh Kumar).
0	If meanings do not match or are not given in the dictionaries .	Collegiate is a word given only in (DK Illustrated Oxford Dictionary) and not in other dictionaries and hence given a score 0 on comparison with (Hawker) and (Dr Suresh Kumar) .

The number of same meanings found compaing 2 dictionaries at a time are shown below .

Figure 2 Number of same meanings taking 2 dictionaries at a time .

Note :Terminologies for dictionaries (D1,D2,D3) are same as given prior to the Hypothesis table above .Terminologies related to proportion are given below .

1. p_{d1}, p_{d2}, p_{d3} – Proportion of (derivatives (adverb , verb , noun , adjective) +origin) of words given in dictionaries 1 ,2 ,3
2. $p_{ds12}, p_{ds23}, p_{ds31}$ - Proportion of same meanings in dictionary 1 and 2 , Proportion of same meanings in dictionary 2 and 3 , Proportion of same meanings in dictionary 3 and 1
3. $p_{ds12max}, p_{ds23max}, p_{ds31max}$ – (Maximum proportion of same meanings possible in dictionary 1 and 2 , Maximum proportion of same meanings possible in dictionary 2 and 3 , Maximum proportion of same meanings possible in dictionary 3 and 1)based on the total number of meanings of 30 words given taking 2 dictionaries at a time

Table 5 Statistical testing using Z test

P _{d1}	P _{d2}	P _{d3}	Criteria	Zcal(p _{d1} - p _{d2})	Zcal(p _{d2} - p _{d3})	Zcal(p _{d3} - p _{d1})	Z _{tab} (5%LOS)	Max(z _{tab} , z _{cal})	Result
0.643	0.929	0.500	Derivatives + origin of words defined	-8.122	-3.358	-3.270	1.96	Zcal(p _{d1} -p _{d2}) Zcal(p _{d2} -p _{d3}) Zcal(p _{d3} -p _{d1})	Null hypothesis (H ₀₁ , H ₀₂ , H ₀₃) rejected

1. There is a significant difference observed between dictionaries 1 and 2, 2 and 3 and 3 and 1 with respect to the proportion of (**derivatives + origin**) of words given in the respective dictionaries.

Table 6 Statistical testing using Z test

P _{ds12}	P _{ds23}	P _{ds31}	Criteria	Zcal(p _{ds12} - -p _{ds12max})	Zcal(p _{ds23} - -p _{ds23max})	Zcal(p _{ds31} - -p _{ds31max})	Z _{tab} (5%LOS)	Max(z _{tab} , z _{cal})	Result
0.407	0.207	0.207	Similarity in meanings of words taking 2 dictionaries at a time	-7.562	-8.271	-6.877	1.96	Zcal(p _{ds12} -p _{ds12max}) Zcal(p _{ds23} -p _{ds23max}) Zcal(p _{ds31} -p _{ds31max})	Null hypothesis (H ₀₄ , H ₀₅ , H ₀₆) rejected

2. There is a significant difference observed in proportion of same meanings between dictionary 1 and 2, 2 and 3 and 3 and 1 and maximum possible proportion of same meanings between dictionaries 1 and 2, 2 and 3 and 3 and 1.

5.2 Findings

1. The words are used in form of different derivatives as noun, verb, adjective, adverb and there is variation observed with respect to number of derivatives given in the 3 dictionaries.

2. The origin of words was in which language and what was its original meaning in that language is mentioned for 15 words and all were specified only in (DK Illustrated Oxford Dictionary, 2011).

3. It is surprising to know that latter versions of the dictionary does not have the words

specified in previous versions in some cases .eg:Eclectic is the word found in (DK Illustrated Oxford Dictionary, 2011) (Hawker, 2014) but not in (Kumar & Sahai, 2014). Ideally a latter version is the development of the previous version .

4.The words like stressor , suboptimal , multiethnic and innumeros are not defined in any of the dictionaries and might be a possibility that these words were registered in the memory of the author because of local usage .This questions the process of word inclusion followed by the dictionaries as language is dynamic but dictionary is static . In a single second thousands of new words take birth because of various soures of variation as shown in figure below when used by different authors.The new editions are published in 2-4 years so the pace of development is actually beating the spirit of customer centric culture in case of dictionaries .

Figure 3 Types of variation in any process

Figure 4 Sources of variation from comparative perspective (Hickmann, Veneziano and Jisa)

Figure 5 Contribution of owner and adopter country to any language

Figure 6 Distribution of words found and not found in all the 3 dictionaries

5.The dictionary authored by Fr.Kamil Bulke (Bulke) is an English-Hindi Dictionary. One of the authors (Dr.Renu) was of the opinion that for students with native language Hindi belonging to the country India English-Hindi Dictionaries are more **learner centric** and serve the purpose better.

6. Some words were found in the dictionaries but they did not list the meanings of the words with respect to other disciplines .for eg :

Table 7 Comparison of meanings of words in Statistical Quality Control and English

Words	Discipline	Definition	English Dictionary
Reliability	Statistical Quality Control	Reliability is the probability of a product functioning in the intended manner over its intended life under the environmental conditions encountered .(M.Mahajan)	Being able to depend on or trusted .
Craftsmanship		It is a theory of motivation of industrial workers ."According to this theory industrial workers have an	It is the ability demonstrated by a worker in a

		internal drive for work and derive satisfaction from good work .”(M.Mahajan)	particular craft.
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7. The probable causes for variation in the content of the dictionaries based on discussion and brainstorming are shown below .

Figure 7 Cause and Effect diagram showing probable reasons of content variation (Based on literature review and brainstorming)

6.Conclusions

- 1.As there is a significant difference in all the 3 dictionaries taking 2 at a time the user should have more than one type of dictionary to be aware about the variation in words .The user wants clarity in content and that can only come with standardized content .Dictionary is having a dynamic content but on a particular day and year there should be one version available in market which is standardized .
- 2.Preferably there must be some agency which should rate dictionaries so that users can base their decision to buy any dictionary based on such ratings by an authentic agency .
- 3.The word inclusion process is to be studied as it is observed that may be because of the regional variations in adopted words from other countries authors have used words which are

not given in any dictionary compared above .After how many usages by how many authors the new words are included in the dictionaries and who is responsible for it is to be studied .The word inclusion should also be studied from the perspective of how inputs are taken from other languages .

4. There is no standard way to compare meanings and hence the comparison results depend on the methodology adopted by the person comparing the meanings .

5.Are dictionaries taking feedback from customers ?If yes ,how they are doing it and what improvements they have done till date based on feedback are important questions to answer .

7.Future Research Directions

1.It will be interesting to know the variation in the meanings derivative wise that is comparison of meanings given as verbs in one dictionary with the meanings given as verbs in the other dictionary and so on .

2.It will be interesting to compare Oxford Dictionaries ,Cambridge Dictionaries and other local dictionaries & their word inclusion processes .

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